
CATPO: CRITIQUE-AUGMENTED TREE POLICY OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Reinforcement learning with verifiable rewards (RLVR) has become a dominant paradigm for improving the reasoning capabilities of large language models (LLMs). Recent tree-based methods such as TREERPO extend flat trajectory sampling with tree-structured rollouts to obtain dense, step-level reward signals without a separate process reward model. However, not all trees are equally informative: trees where all leaves succeed, all leaves fail, or the policy already predicts the reward distribution contribute little to gradient updates, wasting compute. We introduce CATPO (Critique-Augmented Tree Policy Optimization), which diagnoses and addresses this waste at the tree level. CATPO first scores each tree via a *tree informativeness score* $F(T)$, combining leaf-outcome diversity with policy-reward decorrelation at zero extra compute. For dead-wrong trees where all branches fail, CATPO applies *critique-guided healing*: it locates the shallowest failure point, generates a natural-language critique, and grafts refined continuations to recover training signal. Finally, an *informativeness-weighted loss* scales each tree’s gradient contribution by its normalized score, concentrating parameter updates on the most informative trees while preserving overall gradient magnitude. Experiments on Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B trained with the MATH dataset show that CATPO achieves 37.5% macro accuracy across four benchmarks (AIME24, MATH-500, OlympiadBench, MinervaMath), improving over TREERPO by 1.9% and GRPO by 4.8%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent breakthroughs in reinforcement learning have brought transformative progress to large language model (LLM) reasoning. Models such as DeepSeek-R1 (DeepSeek-AI et al., 2025), and QwQ (Team, 2025) achieve remarkable performance on complex reasoning tasks by training with Reinforcement Learning with Verifiable Rewards (RLVR), where the model explores reasoning paths toward correct, automatically checkable answers.

A central challenge in RLVR is credit assignment, trajectory-level rewards reveal whether a solution is right or wrong, but say little about which reasoning steps actually mattered. Two lines of work address this. Process reward models (PRMs) (Lightman et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2024) train separate networks to score each step, but require costly step level annotation. Tree based methods avoid any auxiliary model, by expanding multiple continuations at each step, approaches like TREERPO (Yang et al., 2025) and TreeRL (Hou et al., 2025) estimate step level advantages

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Figure 1: Overview of the CATPO training pipeline. Each iteration proceeds in four phases: (1) sample an N -ary tree of partial solutions and propagate rewards; (2) score each tree with $F(T)$ and classify it into one of four regimes; (3) apply critique-guided healing to dead-wrong trees by finding the failure node, generating a critique, and grafting k refined continuations; (4) scale advantages by the informativeness weight $w(T)$ and update the policy.

from leaf outcomes propagated bottom-up through the tree, yielding dense gradient signal at the cost of only extra sampling.

Yet tree-based methods treat all trees equally in the training loss. In practice, many sampled trees carry little or no useful signal:

- **Dead-correct trees:** all leaves produce the right answer, the model already solves this problem, leaving no contrastive signal.
- **Dead-wrong trees:** every leaf fails, without a single positive branch, group-relative advantages collapse to zero.
- **Stale trees:** the policy’s confidence already tracks the reward distribution, further training yields diminishing returns.

This waste is substantial. DAPO (Yu et al., 2025) and GRESO (Zheng et al., 2025) mitigate the analogous problem for flat rollouts by filtering or predicting uninformative prompts. But these operate at the prompt level, not the tree level: the same prompt can yield an informative tree or a dead one depending on the sample, and the internal structure of the tree - which branches the policy finds surprising - carries signal that prompt-level filtering discards.

We propose **CATPO** (Critique-Augmented Tree Policy Optimization), which tackles this waste directly at the tree level through three complementary mechanisms:

1. **Tree informativeness score.** We define $F(T) = \hat{p}(1-\hat{p}) \cdot (1 - \rho_{\pi,r}^2)$, combining leaf outcome diversity (\hat{p} : leaf pass rate) with policy-reward decorrelation ($\rho_{\pi,r}$: Pearson correlation between node log-probabilities and propagated rewards). Because every ingredient is already computed during tree sampling, $F(T)$ comes at zero additional cost.
2. **Critique-guided healing.** For dead-wrong trees ($F \approx 0$), we locate the shallowest failing depth, prompt the policy model itself to critique the error, and graft k critique conditioned continuations as new branches, recovering training signal from rollouts that would otherwise be wasted.
3. **Informativeness-weighted loss.** Each tree’s contribution to the policy gradient is scaled by its normalized score $w(T) = F(T)/\bar{F}$, modulating advantages and returns so that informative trees drive parameter updates while dead-correct and stale trees receive diminished influence.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 REINFORCEMENT LEARNING FOR LLM REASONING

Reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) (Ouyang et al., 2022) established the paradigm of optimizing LLM policies with reward signals from human preferences. PPO (Schulman et al., 2017) has been the dominant algorithm, though its learned value function introduces instability and overhead. GRPO (Shao et al., 2024) eliminated the value network entirely by using group-normalized rewards as advantage estimates, forming the backbone of breakthroughs like DeepSeek-R1 (DeepSeek-AI et al., 2025). However, GRPO suffers from length and normalization biases (Liu et al., 2025). Subsequent work has refined this paradigm: DAPO (Yu et al., 2025) introduced dynamic sampling and token level policy gradient losses, VAPO (Yue et al., 2025) advocated for value based credit assignment, and RLOO (Ahmadian et al., 2024) and Open-Reasoner-Zero (Hu et al., 2025) showed that simpler REINFORCE style baselines can match or exceed GRPO.

2.2 TREE-BASED RL FOR DENSE REWARD ESTIMATION

Tree structured exploration has roots in inference time methods, Tree-of-Thoughts (Yao et al., 2023), RAP (Hao et al., 2023), and LATS (Zhou et al., 2023), which explore multiple reasoning paths without updating model weights. ReST-MCTS* (Zhang et al., 2024) and rStar-Math (Guan et al., 2025) extended this idea to training time via MCTS for offline self-training. TREEERPO (Yang et al., 2025) was the first to integrate tree sampling into the on-policy RL loop, computing step level advantages via bottom-up reward propagation over sibling nodes. TreeRL (Hou et al., 2025) added entropy guided branching, while TreeGRPO (Ji et al., 2025) and Tree-OPO (Huang et al., 2025) extended tree based advantages to agent tasks and off-policy settings. Crucially, all existing tree based methods treat every tree equally in the training objective. CATPO is the first to *diagnose* tree informativeness and *intervene* on uninformative trees.

2.3 PROCESS REWARD MODELS AND CREDIT ASSIGNMENT

An alternative approach to step level credit assignment trains a separate neural network, a Process Reward Model (PRM), to score intermediate reasoning steps. Let’s Verify Step by Step (Lightman et al., 2024) established that process supervision (per step correctness labels) outperforms outcome supervision for guiding the LLM policy, but requires expensive human annotation. Math-Shepherd (Wang et al., 2024) and OmegaPRM (Luo et al., 2024) automated PRM data collection via Monte Carlo rollouts from intermediate states. PRIME (Cui et al., 2025) computes token level implicit process rewards through a log ratio formulation without explicit PRM training. VinePPO (Kazemnejad et al., 2025) replaces value networks with MC state value estimates for policy optimization, and SPO (Guo et al., 2025) provides segment level credit assignment. These methods improve the quality of advantage estimates for the LLM policy gradient within existing rollout structures. CATPO is complementary, operating at the tree level to filter and repair the rollouts themselves before they are used for policy updates.

2.4 SAMPLE EFFICIENCY IN LLM RL

Wasted compute from uninformative rollouts is a recognized problem. DAPO’s Dynamic Sampling (Yu et al., 2025) filters prompts where all responses succeed or fail. GRESO (Zheng et al., 2025) predicts uninformative prompts before rollout, achieving $2.4\times$ speedup. CDAS (Kong et al., 2025) aligns problem difficulty to model competence. However, these methods operate at the prompt level, they decide whether to train on a problem at all, but cannot diagnose the internal structure of a tree rollout. CATPO operates at the tree level, scoring and repairing the rollout structure itself.

2.5 SELF-CORRECTION AND CRITIQUE FOR LLMs

Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) and Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) demonstrated iterative self-improvement through inference time critique, though Huang et al. (2023) showed that intrinsic self-correction often degrades reasoning without external feedback. SCoRe (Kumar et al., 2024) addressed this via multi-turn online RL, while GLoRe (Havrilla et al., 2024), RISE (Qu et al., 2024),

and DRLC (Cao et al., 2024) trained refinement models on synthetic correction trajectories or used critiques as dense rewards.

CATPO differs structurally, rather than correcting complete trajectories or training a separate refinement model, we apply critique within the tree at the specific point where reasoning first goes wrong, grafting corrected branches while preserving the shared prefix. This is more compute efficient than full regeneration and integrates naturally with the tree-based RL loop.

3 METHODOLOGY

We present CATPO in four parts: background on tree-based RL (Section 3.1), the tree informativeness score (Section 3.2), critique-guided healing (Section 3.3), and the informativeness-weighted training objective (Section 3.4). Figure 1 gives an overview of the full training pipeline.

3.1 BACKGROUND: TREE-BASED RL WITH GRPO

GRPO. Given a prompt q , GRPO (Shao et al., 2024) samples a group of G complete responses $\{o_i\}_{i=1}^G$ from the current LLM policy $\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}$. Each response receives a reward R_i from a rule-based verification function (e.g., checking whether the final answer matches the ground truth). The advantage for response i is computed by normalizing rewards within the group. The LLM policy parameters θ are then updated via a clipped surrogate objective with KL regularization against a reference policy π_{ref} . Crucially, no separate value network or reward model is trained - only the LLM policy is optimized.

TreeRPO. Instead of sampling G independent trajectories, TREERPO (Yang et al., 2025) samples an N -ary tree of depth D from the LLM policy. At each reasoning step, N candidate continuations (each up to L_{step} tokens) are generated, producing a tree where sibling nodes share a common prefix. Leaf nodes are scored by a verification function ϕ , and rewards propagate bottom-up via mean aggregation:

$$r_{\text{node}} = \mathbb{E}_{c \in \text{Children}(v)} [r_c]. \quad (1)$$

Advantages are computed over step-level sibling groups (children of the same parent). For a node with propagated reward r_n and sibling rewards $\{r_s\}$, TREERPO uses a Bernoulli-variance normalization:

$$\hat{A}_n = \frac{r_n - \mu}{\mu(1 - \mu) + \epsilon}, \quad \mu = \text{mean}(\{r_s\}), \quad (2)$$

where $\mu(1 - \mu)$ replaces the empirical standard deviation to maintain consistency between binary and continuous reward normalization. This advantage is replicated across all tokens in the node’s response. No separate value network or reward model is trained.

Limitation. As discussed in Section 1, both GRPO and TREERPO weight all sampled data equally. Zero-variance groups in GRPO become zero-gradient trees in TREERPO, dead-correct, dead-wrong, and stale trees all waste compute. No existing mechanism diagnoses or repairs uninformative trees within the training loop; CATPO fills this gap.

3.2 TREE INFORMATIVENESS SCORE

We propose a *tree informativeness score* that quantifies how useful a tree T is for improving the LLM policy. The score combines two signals available at zero extra cost after tree sampling:

Leaf Diversity Term. Let \hat{p} be the fraction of leaves in T that receive a positive reward. The implementation uses Bernoulli variance:

$$V_B(\hat{p}) = \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}). \quad (3)$$

This term is zero when all leaves agree (all correct or all incorrect), and reaches its maximum 0.25 at $\hat{p} = 0.5$. Intuitively, it measures the amount of contrastive signal available for group-relative advantages.

Policy-Reward Decorrelation. Let $\ell_n = \sum_t \log \pi_\theta(o_{n,t} | q, o_{n,<t})$ be the sum of token log-probabilities for non-root node n under the current policy, and r_n the propagated reward of node n . We compute:

$$\rho_{\pi,r} = \text{Pearson}(\{\ell_n\}_{n \in T \setminus \text{root}}, \{r_n\}_{n \in T \setminus \text{root}}). \quad (4)$$

We use $1 - \rho_{\pi,r}^2$, which is the fraction of reward variation not linearly explained by policy confidence. When $|\rho_{\pi,r}| \approx 1$, the reward structure is largely explained and the tree is less informative; when $\rho_{\pi,r}$ is near 0, learning potential is higher.

Informativeness Score. Combining the leaf diversity term (Eq. 3) with the decorrelation term (Eq. 4), the tree informativeness score is:

$$F(T) = \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}) \cdot (1 - \rho_{\pi,r}^2) \quad (5)$$

with range $[0, 0.25]$. This multiplicative form ensures that both ingredients are necessary, a tree needs diverse outcomes and residual policy uncertainty to yield useful gradients. All quantities are already computed during tree sampling and log-probability evaluation, so $F(T)$ incurs zero additional forward passes.

Tree Classification. Based on $F(T)$, we classify trees into four regimes using thresholds τ_{low} and τ_{high} (Table 1):

Regime	Condition	Interpretation	Action
Dead-correct	$F \leq \tau_{\text{low}}, \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}) < 0.05, \hat{p} > 0.5$	Near-unanimous success	Downweight
Dead-wrong	$F \leq \tau_{\text{low}}, \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}) < 0.05, \hat{p} \leq 0.5$	Near-unanimous failure	Heal via critique
Stale	$\tau_{\text{low}} < F \leq \tau_{\text{high}}$	Moderate residual signal	Moderate weight
Informative	$F > \tau_{\text{high}}$	High learning potential	Full weight

Table 1: Tree classification regimes based on the informativeness score $F(T)$. We use $\tau_{\text{low}}=0.025$ and $\tau_{\text{high}}=0.10$ for $F \in [0, 0.25]$.

3.3 CRITIQUE-GUIDED HEALING

Dead-wrong trees ($F \approx 0$, all leaves incorrect) represent problems where the model consistently fails. Rather than discarding them, CATPO attempts to heal them by introducing corrected branches via natural-language critique.

Step 1: Identify the Failure Point. We perform a breadth-first search from the root to find the shallowest depth d^* where all children have propagated reward $r_c < \epsilon$ (with $\epsilon = 0.05$). This is the point where reasoning first goes entirely wrong.

Step 2: Generate a Critique. The original problem text (from the root node) and the partial solution text (from the root to the failing node at depth d^*) are decoded. The policy model itself is prompted to identify the specific error:

Critique Prompt

You are a mathematical reasoning critic. A student attempted the following problem but got it wrong.
 Problem: {Problem text}
 Student’s partial solution: {Partial solution}
 Task: Identify the specific mathematical or logical error. Be precise about which step is wrong and why.

The critique is generated at low temperature ($\tau = 0.3$) to produce a focused error diagnosis.

Step 3: Graft Refined Continuations. The policy model is then prompted with the problem, the partial solution, and the generated critique, and asked to produce k corrected continuations. These are scored by the verification function and added as new children of the failing node (at depth $d^* + 1$), alongside the original failing children:

Refinement Prompt

Problem text
 A student’s incorrect attempt: {Partial solution}
 Critique of the error: {Critique text}
 Provide a corrected solution continuing from where the error was found. Show your work step by step.

Each refinement is generated at the standard sampling temperature ($\tau = 0.6$), tokenized, truncated to L_{step} tokens, and scored by the verification function to obtain a leaf reward.

Step 4: Re-score and Re-propagate. The new leaves are scored by the verification function, rewards are re-propagated bottom-up via Eq. 1, and the informativeness score $F(T)$ is recomputed. If healing succeeds, some refined branches produce correct answers, converting a dead-wrong tree into one with positive reward diversity. We validate this empirically in Section 4 (H2).

3.4 CATPO TRAINING OBJECTIVE

After healing, all nodes original and grafted are treated uniformly. Each tree’s contribution to the policy gradient is weighted by its normalized informativeness:

$$w(T) = \frac{F(\tilde{T})}{\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{T' \in \mathcal{B}} F(\tilde{T}')} \tag{6}$$

where \tilde{T} denotes the tree after healing. This normalization preserves the overall gradient magnitude while redistributing it toward informative trees. The weight $w(T)$ is treated as a detached constant during backpropagation; gradients do not flow through the informativeness computation. We adopt the clipped surrogate objective of TREERPO with this per-tree weight:

$$\mathcal{J}_{\text{CATPO}}(\theta) = \sum_{T \in \mathcal{B}} w(T) \sum_{n \in T} \frac{1}{|O_n|} \sum_{t=1}^{|O_n|} \left(\min(r_{n,t}(\theta) \hat{A}_{n,t}, \text{clip}(r_{n,t}(\theta), 1 - \varepsilon, 1 + \varepsilon) \hat{A}_{n,t}) - \beta D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_\theta \| \pi_{\text{ref}}) \right) \tag{7}$$

where $r_{n,t}(\theta)$ is the standard importance ratio and $\hat{A}_{n,t}$ is the Bernoulli-variance-normalized advantage (Eq. 2). Following TREERPO, only non-root nodes whose sibling reward range exceeds $\tau_{\text{prune}} = 0.1$ participate. Grafted nodes from healing enter the same computation without modification, the informativeness weight is the only difference from TREERPO.

The complete algorithm is summarized in Appendix A.

4 EXPERIMENTS

4.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Datasets. We follow the TREERPO experimental protocol. For training, we use the training split of the MATH dataset (Hendrycks et al., 2021), which contains 7.5k high-quality mathematical reasoning problems. For evaluation, we report results on four widely used benchmarks: MATH-500 (Lightman et al., 2024) (500 representative problems from the MATH test split), Olympiad-Bench (He et al., 2024), MinervaMath (Lewkowycz et al., 2022), and AIME24.

Base Models. Our experiments use the Qwen2.5-Math series (Yang et al., 2024). We report results on Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B.

Method	AIME24	MATH-500	OlympiadBench	Minerva	Macro Acc.
<i>Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B as the Base Model</i>					
GRPO	13.8	67.9	28.5	20.5	32.7
TREERPO	16.8 \uparrow 3.0	70.7 \uparrow 2.8	30.9 \uparrow 2.4	24.0 \uparrow 3.5	35.6 \uparrow 2.9
CATPO	20.3 \uparrow 6.5	71.8 \uparrow 3.9	33.1 \uparrow 4.6	24.8 \uparrow 4.3	37.5 \uparrow 4.8

Table 2: Overall *Pass@1* (Avg@8) performance on four mathematical reasoning benchmarks.

Baselines. We compare against:

- **GRPO** (Shao et al., 2024): flat trajectory sampling with group-relative advantages.
- **TREERPO** (Yang et al., 2025): tree-structured sampling with step-level group-relative advantages (our direct base method).

Implementation Details. We build on the rllm framework¹ derived from verl (Sheng et al., 2025), with vLLM (Kwon et al., 2023) for efficient inference. For GRPO: temperature 0.6, 8 rollouts per prompt, batch size 128, learning rate 1e-6, max response length 1152. For TREERPO and CATPO : temperature 0.6, branching factor $N = 8$, max depth $D = 3$, max step length $L_{\text{step}} = 384$, pruning threshold $\tau = 0.1$. CATPO -specific: $\tau_{\text{low}} = 0.025$, $\tau_{\text{high}} = 0.10$, dead-tree variance cutoff $\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}) < 0.05$, and $k = 4$ refinements. KL coefficient $\beta = 0.001$, entropy loss coefficient $\alpha = -0.001$. All experiments are conducted on a single A100-80GB GPU. Full hyperparameters and software details are provided in Appendix B (Tables 4–6).

Metrics. We report **Pass@1** (**Avg@8**) accuracy: for each test problem, 8 responses are sampled at temperature 0.6, and accuracy is averaged across samples. This differs from standard *Pass@k*, which measures whether *any* of k samples is correct; our metric reports the mean binary correctness across all 8 samples. We report individual benchmark scores and the **Macro Accuracy** (unweighted average across four benchmarks).

4.2 HYPOTHESIS VALIDATION

We validate the two core hypotheses that motivate our design: (H1) the informativeness score $F(T)$ is a meaningful proxy for how much a tree contributes to the policy gradient, and (H2) critique-guided healing can recover useful signal from dead-wrong trees.

H1: Informativeness Predicts Gradient Utility. We build trees offline for 100 problems from the MATH training set using Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B, compute $F(T)$ for each tree, and measure the per-tree gradient norm $\|g(T)\|^2$ via REINFORCE-style forward-backward passes. If $F(T)$ is a good proxy for training utility, it should correlate positively with $\|g(T)\|^2$.

Correlation Metric	Value	<i>p</i> -value
Pearson r	0.54	4.1e-05
Spearman ρ	0.62	1.7e-06

Table 3: Correlation between tree informativeness score $F(T)$ and per-tree gradient norm $\|g(T)\|^2$ on 50 trees from MATH training set.

As shown in Table 3, the tree informativeness score $F(T)$ exhibits a strong positive correlation with per-tree gradient norms, with Spearman $\rho = 0.62$ ($p = 1.7e-06$). The relationship is monotonic but not perfectly linear: trees with very low informativeness ($F < 0.025$) consistently produce near-zero gradient norms, confirming that dead-correct and dead-wrong trees are indeed uninformative

¹<https://github.com/agentica-project/rllm>

for the policy update. In the mid-range ($0.025 < F < 0.10$), gradient norms increase steadily, while the most informative trees ($F > 0.10$) produce the largest gradients, though with greater variance, reflecting the fact that some informative trees contain harder problems where the gradient direction is useful but noisy. A small number of outliers appear at moderate F with unusually high gradient norms, inspection reveals these correspond to problems at the boundary of the model’s competence where a single correct branch among many failures creates a strong contrastive signal. Overall, H1 validates that $F(T)$ is a reliable, zero-cost proxy for gradient utility, justifying its use as an informativeness weight in the training loss.

H2: Critique Heals Dead-Wrong Trees. From the same tree set, we select all dead-wrong trees ($F \leq 0.025$, $\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p}) < 0.05$, $\hat{p} \leq 0.5$) and apply critique-guided healing with $k = 4$ refinements and measure the informativeness improvement percentage.

Of the dead-wrong trees subjected to healing, 88.1% show a positive improvement in F , indicating that the critique then refine pipeline successfully introduces at least one correct branch in the majority of cases. The remaining trees where healing fails ($\Delta F = 0$) correspond to problems that are fundamentally beyond the model’s current capability: the critique correctly identifies the error, but the refined continuations repeat similar mistakes. This is consistent with prior findings that self-correction without external feedback is bounded by model capability (Huang et al., 2023). Notably, healing is most effective when the failure occurs at a shallow depth (depth 1), where the critique has access to a short, focused error trace rather than a long chain of compounding mistakes. Using the policy model as its own critic avoids the inference cost of a separate model while leveraging the policy’s own understanding of its reasoning process. While this validates that critique-guided healing mechanistically restores gradient signal in dead-wrong trees, the downstream impact on policy accuracy is confirmed by the main results in Table 2.

4.3 MAIN RESULTS

As shown in Table 2, CATPO achieves a Macro Accuracy of 37.5% on Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B, improving over TREERPO by 1.9% and over GRPO by 4.8%. The gains are consistent across all four benchmarks, but notably larger on the harder evaluation sets (AIME24 and OlympiadBench) than on MATH-500. This pattern is expected: harder problems produce a higher proportion of dead-wrong trees under the baseline, giving CATPO more opportunities to recover training signal through both informativeness weighting and critique healing. On MATH-500, where the model already achieves reasonable accuracy under TREERPO, fewer trees fall into the dead-wrong regime, so the margin is naturally smaller. The substantial improvement on Minerva a benchmark outside the MATH training distribution suggests that informativeness-weighted training helps the model learn more transferable reasoning strategies rather than overfitting to the training domain.

5 CONCLUSION

We introduced CATPO, a method that enhances tree-based reinforcement learning for training LLM reasoning policies through three complementary mechanisms, a zero-cost tree informativeness score that identifies which trees carry the most useful signal for the policy gradient, a critique-guided healing procedure that recovers training signal from dead-wrong trees, and an informativeness-weighted loss that concentrates parameter updates on informative trees. Our informativeness score $F(T)$ combines leaf-level diversity with policy-reward decorrelation to quantify each tree’s learning potential, and we validated that it correlates with per-tree gradient norms and that critique healing significantly increases the informativeness of failing trees. By scaling the policy gradient loss with normalized tree informativeness, CATPO redistributes gradient contributions toward the most useful rollouts while rescuing otherwise wasted compute through critique-guided healing.

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A ALGORITHM

The complete algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 CATPO : Critique-Augmented Tree Policy Optimization

Require: LLM policy π_θ , reference policy π_{ref} , training data \mathcal{D} , branching factor N , max depth D , refinements k , thresholds $\tau_{\text{low}}, \tau_{\text{high}}$

- 1: **for** each training iteration **do**
 - 2: Sample batch of prompts $\{q_i\}$ from \mathcal{D}
 - 3: **Phase 1:** For each q_i , sample N -ary tree T_i of depth D ; score leaves; propagate rewards bottom-up; compute sibling-relative advantages (Eq. 2); prune low-variance sibling groups; compute $\log \pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}$ for all non-pruned nodes
 - 4: **Phase 2:** Compute $F(T_i) = \hat{p}_i(1 - \hat{p}_i) \cdot (1 - \rho_{\pi, r_i}^2)$ using the log-probs from Phase 1; classify each tree
 - 5: **Phase 3:** For each dead-wrong tree T_i (where $F(T_i) \leq \tau_{\text{low}}$, $\hat{p}_i(1 - \hat{p}_i) < 0.05$, and $\hat{p}_i \leq 0.5$):
 - 6: Find shallowest node v^* where all children have $r_c < \epsilon$
 - 7: Decode problem text (from root) and partial solution (from root to v^*)
 - 8: Generate critique at temperature $\tau=0.3$
 - 9: Generate k refined continuations at temperature $\tau=0.6$
 - 10: Graft as children of v^* ; score with verification function; re-propagate rewards; recompute advantages
 - 11: **Phase 4:** Compute informativeness weights $w(T_i) = F(\tilde{T}_i)/\bar{F}$; scale advantages by $w(T_i)$
 - 12: Update θ via $\nabla_\theta \mathcal{J}_{\text{CATPO}}(\theta)$ (Eq. 7)
 - 13: **end for**
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B IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

We provide full implementation details for reproducibility. All experiments are built on the `rllm` framework² derived from `verl` (Sheng et al., 2025), using `vLLM` (Kwon et al., 2023) as the roll-out engine with the `XFORMERS` attention backend. Training uses PyTorch 2.4 with FSDP for distributed training and gradient checkpointing enabled throughout.

B.1 MODEL AND DATA

We use Qwen2.5-Math-1.5B as the base model. The training data is the MATH dataset (Hendrycks et al., 2021) formatted as chain-of-thought parquet files with `<think>` delimiters, which are ignored during reward computation (`ignore_think=True`). Prompts are truncated to 512 tokens.

B.2 OPTIMIZATION HYPERPARAMETERS

Table 4 summarizes the optimization and batching hyperparameters.

²<https://github.com/agentica-project/rllm>

Table 4: Optimization and batching hyperparameters.

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	1×10^{-6}
LR warmup ratio	0.0
PPO epochs per iteration	1
PPO clip ratio ϵ	0.2
PPO mini-batch size	16
Gradient clipping	1.0
KL loss type	low-var KL
KL loss coefficient β	0.001
KL control coefficient	0.001
Train batch size	32
Validation batch size	128
Max prompt length	512 tokens
Max response length	1152 tokens
Dynamic batch sizing	✓
Max tokens per GPU	12288

B.3 TREE STRUCTURE AND CATPO-SPECIFIC HYPERPARAMETERS

Table 5 details the hyperparameters governing tree rollouts (shared by TreeRPO and CATPO) and the CATPO-specific critique-healing parameters.

Table 5: Tree rollout and CATPO-specific hyperparameters.

Hyperparameter	Value
<i>Tree Structure (TreeRPO & CATPO)</i>	
Branching factor N	8
Step length L_{step}	384 tokens
Max depth $D = \lceil 1152/384 \rceil$	3
Sampling temperature	0.6
Validation temperature	0.6
Validation rollouts n_{val}	8
<i>CATPO-Specific</i>	
Informativeness threshold τ_{low}	0.025
Informativeness threshold τ_{high}	0.10
Dead-tree variance cutoff	0.05
Healing failure threshold ϵ	0.05
Critique temperature	0.3
Critique max tokens	256
Refinement temperature	0.6
Number of refinements k	4

B.4 INFRASTRUCTURE

All experiments run on a single NVIDIA A100-80GB GPU. Table 6 lists infrastructure and training schedule settings.

Table 6: Infrastructure and training schedule.

Setting	Value
GPUs	1×A100-80GB
Tensor parallel size	1
FSDP parameter offload	×
FSDP optimizer offload	✓
Reference model param offload	✓
vLLM GPU memory utilization	0.5
Total epochs	30
Checkpoint frequency	every 20 steps
Evaluation frequency	every 20 steps